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ACTES DU COLLOQUE
« LES TROUVAILLES DE MONNAIES
ROMAINES EN CONTEXTE MÉDIÉVAL »

CEN - BRUXELLES

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CENTRE EUROPÉEN D'ÉTUDES NUMISMATIQUES

BRUXELLES

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THE CIRCULATION OF COPPER COINS IN THE IBERIAN PENINSULA DURING THE VISIGOTHIC PERIOD: NEW APPROACHES

Ruth PLIEGO*

Abstract – This paper addresses the issue of Visigothic copper coins and presents an overview of the current state of our knowledge, challenging a number of ideas that are currently accepted, despite the lack of evidence. The paper revisits typologies and proposes a revised chronology. Similarly, these *nummi* are presented within the wider framework of coin issues

in other Germanic kingdoms, thus illustrating the parallels and differences between them. Finally, the nature of these monetary issues is examined, and a distinction is made between those backed by royal and municipal authorities, including the unofficial issues fostered by the latter.

Keywords: Numismatic – Early Medieval Numismatic – Visigoths – Visigothic coinage – bronze coinage – *Nummi* – *Nummus* – Iberian Peninsula – Late Antiquity – Economy of the Mediterranean Sea – Early Middle Ages – 6th c. – 7th c. – Barbarian kingdoms

Résumé – Cet article traite de la question des monnaies de bronze wisigoths. On présente un aperçu de l'état des connaissances, contestant un certain nombre d'idées actuellement acceptées malgré le manque de preuves. Les typologies sont revisitées et une nouvelle chronologie est proposée. Ces *nummi* sont par la

suite présentés dans le cadre plus large des autres royaumes germaniques, illustrant ainsi les parallèles et les différences entre eux. Enfin, la nature de ces questions monétaires est examinée et une distinction est faite entre les monnayages royaux et municipaux, y compris les frappes non-officielles de ces derniers.

Mots clés : numismatique – Antiquité tardive – Wisigoth – monnaies de bronze – *nummi* – *nummus* – péninsule Ibérique – économie de la Méditerranée – VI^e s. – VII^e s. – royaumes barbares.

* Research projects: 'La invención del pagano: Las fronteras de la identidad religiosa en el mundo tardoantiguo' (HAR-2014-51946). Member of the research groups 'De la Turdetania a la Bética' (HUM-152). I wish to thank E. García Vargas and T. Ibrahim for revising the manuscript and for their suggestions.

STRUCTURE DE L'ÉTUDE

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2. THE TYPOLOGIES
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7. THE LOCATION: MINTS?
8. THE ISSUING AUTHORITY
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11. CONCLUSIONS

1. INTRODUCTION

“THE VISIGOTHS ONLY ISSUED GOLD COINS”. To date, this statement has been an unimpeachable dogma. The purpose of this work is to demonstrate that the Visigoths also issued copper coins^[1]. These words opened Miquel Crusafont’s *El sistema monetario visigodo: cobre y oro*, which presented the little-known material which he had compiled over the years^[2]. This material included small bronze and copper coins which presented a very schematic typology and seemed to be of very crude workmanship, nevertheless human figures, inscriptions and monograms can be identified. The crude technique and the poor state of preservation of these pieces explain their near-total absence from excavation inventories that predate Crusafont’s publication, with the exception of the excavation at L’Illa Cullera (Valencia)^[3]. Their late incorporation into numismatic research is also explained by their limited value to collectors. However, recent interest in the historical facts, rather than in the pieces’ economic value, has brought a considerable, and hitherto unknown, repertoire to the surface. These issues belong to a group of bronze types generally known as *nummi*, which were issued between the 4th and, at least, the 7th c. Despite being ‘small, poorly struck, worn and corroded’, they are of enormous value for the study of Late Antiquity in the Mediterranean^[4].

2. THE TYPOLOGIES

First, it is necessary to present the typologies which are known to date. No analysis is intended at this point: this section is solely concerned with the description of the published types. Sixteen different groups have been identified, including twelve which were already presented by Crusafont (Groups A-E; F.48-F53; *addenda*) and three that were published elsewhere. The equivalences with Crusafont’s groups, as well as the bibliographic references to the three latter types, have been included. I am aware that this classification will change, as it does not take into consideration a number of collections such as the De la Oliva – the most important private repertoire, which includes nearly 300 pieces found in Seville and its province^[5] – or Cores and Archivo Tonegawa – both also from Seville – in which new types have already been identified. The pieces from Churriana (Malaga) have also been excluded for reasons that will be explained in due course, as well as a coin found in Clermont-Ferrand (France) which is still awaiting publication^[6]. The sole purpose of this classification is to present an alternative denomination to guide us in the following sections.

Visigothic bronze coin typologies:

1. ‘Bust right/ERM’ (Crusafont 1994, Addenda)
2. ‘SP’ (Crusafont 1994, Groups A and B)
3. ‘Bust right/Monogram’ (Crusafont 1994, Group C)
4. ‘Head left *civitas*/Monogram’ (Crusafont 1994, Group C)
5. ‘Bust right with sceptre’ (Crusafont 1994, Group D)
6. ‘Head left/Forked cross’ (Crusafont 1994, Group E)

[1] Crusafont 1994.

[2] His first work on this issue was published three years earlier (see Crusafont 1988).

[3] Mateu 1958 and 1972.

[4] Moorhead 2013, p. 601.

[5] Apparently, they were found primarily in a country house in the village of Tomares.

[6] I wish to thank V. Geneviève for this information.

Fig. 1 – Typologies of Visigoth's copper. 1: 'Bust r./ERM'. 2a: 'Front bust/SP' (1.65 g; 13.55 mm; 2.2 mm. De la Oliva Collection, Seville). 2B: 'Cross on step/SP' (0.34 g; 7 mm; 2 mm. De la Oliva Collection, Seville). 3: 'Bust r./Monogram' (0.70 g; 9.5 mm; 2 mm. De la Oliva Collection, Seville). 4: 'Head/Bust l./ Monogram' (1.31 g; 10 mm; 2 mm. De la Oliva Collection, Seville). 5: 'Bust r. with sceptre/Monogram' (0.84 g; 9.2 mm. Künker Auction 205 (2012/3/12) n° 1354). 6: 'Head l./Forked cross' (1.90 g; 11.5 mm; 3 mm. De la Oliva Collection, Seville). 7: 'Head l. or r./Forked cross with globules in quadrants' (0.95 g; 11.7 mm. Calle Cañón-Postigo de los abades, Málaga. Mora & Martínez 2008, n° 15). 8: 'Frontal bust/ Forked cross with globules in quadrants' (0.95 g; 10 mm. Menorca. Moll 2005, n° 34). 9: 'Bust l./Cross and globules' (1.46 g; 11 mm; 3 mm. De la Oliva Collection, Seville). 10: 'Head r./Doubly globuled cross' (0.92 g; 9.5 mm. Crusafont 1994, n° 228). 11: 'Head l./Monogram (BP?)' (2.62 g; 11 mm. Crusafont 1994, n° 227). 12: 'Encircled cross/Encircled cross' (1.10 g; 10.3 mm. Crusafont 1994, n° 223). 13: 'Cross/Cross' (0.48 g; 7 mm; 2 mm. De la Oliva Collection, Seville). 14: 'Cross/A' (0.66 g; 9 mm. Forvm's Classical Numismatics (May 08, 2011). 15: 'Monogram: RCD./Monogram: SPAL' (0.47 g; 10 mm; 1 mm; 1 h. De la Oliva Collection, Seville) (Pliego 2009, t. I, p. 189). 16: 'Cross/Delta' (1.05 g; 11.7 mm. Theatre of Cartagena)

7. 'Head left/Forked cross with globules in quadrants' (Mora & Martínez 2008)
8. 'Frontal bust/Forked cross with globules' (Moll 2005)
9. 'Bust left/Cross and globules' (Crusafont 1994, Group F.48)
10. 'Head right/Doubly globuled cross' (Crusafont 1994, Group F.53)
11. 'Head left/Monogram (BP?)' (Crusafont 1994, Group F.52)
12. 'Encircled cross/Encircled cross' (Crusafont 1994, Group F.49)
13. 'Cross/Cross' (Crusafont 1994, Group 51)
14. 'Cross/A' (Crusafont 1994, Group F.50)
15. 'Monogram RCD?/Monogram SPAL' (Pliego 2009, 188)
16. 'Cross/Delta' (Lechuga 2000).

3. CRUSAFONT'S WORK

Crusafont's most important contribution was the compilation of all of these bronze pieces, a total of 229 if we include the coin in his *addenda*. Despite the fact that most of them were out of context, we know that the majority came from the southern Iberian Peninsula, specifically Seville and its hinterland. Based on the material evidence, Crusafont created several groups according to typology, metrology and, whenever possible, inscriptions and monograms. The author dated all of these groups to the Visigothic period. His chronology was chiefly based on typological criteria. The five most important groups were related to major Visigothic cities: *Hispalis* (Groups A and B), *Emerita* (Group C), *Toledo* (Group D) and *Cordoba* (Group E) (fig. 1).

The first two groups were related to the mint of *Hispalis*^[7] because both present the letters SP on one side (sometimes linked by an L). According to the author, in *pentanumia* (Group B) the inscription appears under the arms of a cross^[8]. The obverse of coins in Group B (fig. 1.2a) presents a frontal bust that could, in Crusafont's opinion, be assimilated to the frontal busts on gold coins^[9]. The obverse of the smaller denomination (Group A) (fig. 1.2b), which Crusafont^[10] identified as a *nummus*, presents a cross above two steps. Obviously, the inscription was read as *SP(ali)* and *SP(a)L(i)*. Concerning chronology, based on the typology on the obverse of Group A, Crusafont proposed a date during Leovigild's reign (c. 575-586), or even Recceswinth's (649-672), during whose reign this typology re-emerged on gold coins^[11]. On the other hand, based on typology, Group B was dated to Chintila's reign (636-639), although a date in the final years of Leovigild's reign (post 584) could also be correct.

Crusafont's Group C, attributed to *Emerita*, presents on its obverse a bust to the left or a simplified bust, probably facing right (fig. 1.3-4) – sometimes the bust looks like a head – and sometimes portrayed with a diadem, but not in every case. In the few examples where this typology appears in full, it clearly includes an inscription, which seems to read *Civitas*. The monogram on the reverse is some sort of M with loops on the upper angles, which are linked by a straight line that runs above the lower angles. Sometimes these lower angles are engraved towards this straight line. In most cases, the bases of the shafts are stressed, but there is much

^[7] Crusafont 1994, p. 52-53, 58-60.

^[8] Crusafont 1994, p. 48.

^[9] Frontal busts were introduced by Leovigild in c. 584 and lasted until the reign of Chindasvinto (649) (see Pliego 2009, I, p. 156ff).

^[10] Crusafont 1994, p. 48.

^[11] Crusafont 1994, p. 51.

variety in the execution of both obverse and reverse. Crusafont believed that the central body of the type was an “M”, while the loops were the letter “e” in minor case, the first one retrograde. This combination appears in other kinds of documents and was interpreted as *EME(rita)*^[12] (fig. 2a). The diversity of these coins also concerns metrology, and Crusafont suggested that we could well be facing more than one denomination, maybe 2½ *nummi* and *pentanumion*^[13]. This variability also led Crusafont to propose a wide chronology for these issues, which may have begun during Leovigild’s reign.

Fig. 2 – Crusafont Monogram’s interpretation (types 3-4 and 5)

Group D (fig. 1.5) also presents a bust with diadem – visible in the best-preserved examples – to the right. The character seems to be holding a cross-shaped sceptre, a typology which is common on gold coins from the reign of Wamba (672-687) onwards, which led Crusafont to date these issues to the initial years of this reign^[14] (fig. 3). The reverse presents a design which could be related to the letter M found in the previous group; the angles and the loops are, however, more schematic and are not linked to the vertical shafts. They converge on the upper central angle, which is also the base for a cross that occupies the interior. Crusafont sees two small T, the second of which is retrograde, and thus interprets *T(ole)T(o)*^[15] (fig. 2b). Metrology suggests that the denomination is 2 1/2 *nummi*^[16].

Fig. 3 – Tremisis of Wamba (672-680).
x2 Toletó. 1,50 g; 20 mm (Kung. Myntkabinettet Nationalmuseum, Stockholm)

Finally, the obverse of Group E presents a highly schematic and poorly preserved – at least in the recorded examples – head to the left, while the reverse presents an equilateral cross with forked ends (fig. 1.6). There is no letter or monogram with which to relate the group to a specific mint, although Crusafont^[17] suggests *Cordoba* based on the bust-less head and the equilateral cross, which were known types of golden coins issued by the Cordoban mint.

[12] Crusafont 1994, p. 54-57, 60-61.

[13] Crusafont 1994, p. 48.

[14] Crusafont 1994, p. 51.

[15] Crusafont 1994, p. 57, 61.

[16] Crusafont 1994, p. 57, 61.

[17] Crusafont 1994, p. 62.

Metrology, albeit based on a limited number of examples, suggests that we are dealing with a *pentanumion*, while the lack of bust indicates a chronology during Chintila's reign^[18].

In addition to the abovementioned types, Crusafont grouped other types under the label 'Uncertain mints' (Group F: n° 48-53), which present busts to the left (n° 48, 52) (fig. 1.9 and 1.11) and right (n° 53) (fig. 1.10), and reverses with a cross (n° 48, 53) (fig. 1.9 and 1.10), as well as a typology with some sort of "A" on the obverse and a cross on the reverse (n° 50) (fig. 1.14), and another with a cross on both the obverse and reverse (n° 51) (fig. 1.13), sometimes with encircled inscriptions (n° 49) (fig. 1.12). Despite its homogeneity, the reverse of n° 52 is difficult to interpret, although a "P" can be deciphered and, more doubtfully, a "B" (fig. 1.11). Finally, Crusafont's *addenda* included a piece that appears to present the name of a Visigothic king: *ERM(enegild)* (fig. 1.1). The following table summarises the typologies presented by Crusafont (fig. 4).

Eventually, Crusafont placed the, mostly decontextualised, finds on the map. These locations, in the south and east of the Iberian Peninsula, have undergone few changes over the years.

Group		Mint	Description	Value	Starting date	Find spot
A		<i>Hispalis</i>	SP/Cross on steps	<i>N</i>	Leovigild (575-586) or Recceswinth (649-672)	Seville
B		<i>Hispalis</i>	Frontal bust/SP Cross	<i>P</i>	Chintila (636-639)	Seville
C		<i>Emerita?</i>	Bust/right; Head left; <i>civitas</i> /Monogram	2+1/2 <i>N</i> or <i>P</i>	Leovigild (575-586) or Wamba (672-680)	Seville, Cullera
D		<i>Toledo?</i>	Bust right with sceptre	2+1/2 <i>N</i>	Wamba (672-680)	Seville, Cullera
E		<i>Cordoba?</i>	Head left/Forked cross	<i>P</i>	Chintila (636-639)	Seville, Cullera
F	48		Bust left/Globuled cross	-	-	Seville
	49		Encircled cross/Idem	-	-	Seville
	50		A/Cross	-	-	Seville
	51		Cross/Cross	-	-	Seville
	52		Head left/Monogram (BP?)	-	-	Seville
	53		Head right/Doubly globuled cross	-	-	Seville
Addenda			Bust right/ERM	-	-	Seville

Fig. 4 – Crusafont's typologies. Abbreviations: N: nummus/nummi; P: pentanumion.

Locations include different places near Seville (Salteras, Coria del Río, Alcalá del Río, San Juan de Aznalfarache, Montequinto, El Palmar de Troya and Utrera), as well as L'Illa de Cullera (Valencia) – which was known from much earlier^[19] – Cartagena and Menorca, as well as other lesser-known places such as Mengíbar. I shall return to these later, along with more recent locations.

^[18] Crusafont 1994, p. 48, 50.

^[19] Mateu 1958 and 1972.

The key ideas of Crusafont's work were as follows:

- The Visigothic monetary system included gold and copper-bronze coins, and was therefore 'at least bimetallic'^[20]
- Groups with SP/SPL (A-B) are associated with certainty with *Hispalis*. The association of Groups C and D with *Emerita* and *Toledo* is likely, although 'the singularity of the monograms prevents a more resolute conclusion'^[21]. Group E must remain tentatively attributed to *Cordoba*.
- The circulation of small copper-bronze coins in the Visigothic period is clear: 'even if the Visigothic adscription were not accepted, the fact that small-denomination bronzes were in circulation can hardly be denied. This circulation was based on local issues, as well as Byzantine and Vandal pieces'.
- These issues responded to monetary needs brought to the fore by the presence of the Byzantines^[22].
- Although 'issues outside the authority of the Visigothic crown are not to be considered'... 'some initiative on the part of the Church, with monarchic authorisation and ultimate endorsement, cannot be discarded'. Crusafont's final conclusion is that 'Visigothic coppers were small coins for everyday exchange ... For this reason, one of the lessons that we ought to learn is that, quite apart from the ruling elites, the people also make their contribution to history'^[23].

4. LATER RESEARCH

Despite the increasing number of specimens available, later researchers criticised Crusafont's work, especially his methodology, which has somewhat obscured the importance of the material itself. The earliest criticisms of Crusafont's work came from T. Marot, firstly in conjunction with M^a M. Lloréns^[24], and later on her own^[25]. Although Marot admits that these coins must have been issued in the Iberian Peninsula, she stresses the fact that they are not found solely in areas under Visigothic control, but also in the eastern regions 'under the domination or the obvious Byzantine influence in the second half of the 6th c.^[26]'. This does not clash with Crusafont's thesis, who, in any case, claims that 'a significant proportion' of these pieces 'have systematically appeared in Visigothic areas'^[27].

Similarly, Marot^[28] considers that the basis of the arguments used to divide the pieces into different groups and mints is meagre, especially concerning Group E (Type 6), something which, as we have seen, Crusafont himself admits by reducing this attribution to the category of hypothesis. Marot's criticism, however, largely revolves around Crusafont's chronological definition of each group, which in her opinion is contradicted by the archaeological evidence. In general, Marot's arguments are based on data extracted from the excavation

^[20] Crusafont 1994, p. 107.

^[21] Crusafont 1994, p. 106.

^[22] Crusafont 1994, p. 93.

^[23] Crusafont 1994, p. 64 and 107.

^[24] Marot & Lloréns 1996.

^[25] Chiefly Marot 1997; 2000-2001.

^[26] Marot 2001, p. 145.

^[27] Crusafont 1994, p. 30.

^[28] Marot 2001, p. 146; Marot & Llorens 1996, p. 161.

of L'Illa de Cullera, which I shall examine in detail later. In addition, Marot also questions Crusafont's arguments concerning the issuing authority: 'archaeological evidence challenges the chronology and the identification of the issuing authorities as well as the place where the coins were struck'. Ultimately, the debate revolved around the question of what person or institution had the authority to issue coins, a debate that has turned into a heated, and sometimes unreasonable, controversy.

Marot's publications coincided with the increased use of metal detectors in archaeology^[29], which increased the recovery of small pieces. In fact, most of the works that followed Crusafont and Marot report the discovery of copper coins in stratigraphic contexts, for example in Cartagena^[30], Malaga^[31], Sevilla and its province^[32], Menorca^[33] and Tolmo de Minateda (Hellín, Albacete)^[34]. The identification of new issues has also triggered the publication of a number of decontextualised specimens in Seville^[35] and, more doubtfully, as we shall see, Malaga^[36].

Apart from the find reports, these coins have also been mentioned in more general works, in particular the *Corpus Nummorum Visigothorum*^[37], which, despite being a catalogue for collectors, puts forward several influential ideas concerning these types. From another perspective, J. Vizcaíno's excellent *La presencia bizantina en Hispania* included these bronze issues in its discussion of numismatic evidence and compiled all the information available at the time of publication^[38]. I have also treated the issue in my work *La moneda visigoda*^[39], including the publication of several new examples. Other works include M. Metcalf, F. Retamero, J. S. Huffstot and I. Martín Viso, among others^[40]. We have already mentioned the controversy initiated by Marot's reaction to Crusafont's work, a controversy which essentially revolves around chronology and the attribution of each of Crusafont's series to a mint and an issuing authority. As we shall see, later works have essentially followed Marot's lead. In the following sections, I shall address each of these topics in turn, instead of taking a diachronic approach. However, before we do so it is convenient to update the *corpus* of finds.

5. THE FINDS

As aforementioned, the examples found in L'Illa de Cullera (Valencia) were the first to be published^[41]. These types, however, have not been found during excavations in this area since,

^[29] See Fernández Flores 2003b.

^[30] Lechuga 2000, 2005; Vizcaíno 2007, p. 687-725.

^[31] Mora 2001a-b, 2005 and 2009; Mora & Martínez 2008.

^[32] Fernández Flores 2003a; Fernández Flores, Pliego & Carvajal 2013; Garrido & Escudero 2013.

^[33] Moll 2005. These specimens are in a private collection. A recent numismatic analysis of the material from Puerto de Sanitja (Sanisera, Menorca) has revealed 116 Roman, Vandal and unidentified coins, none of which belong to the typologies under consideration (see Bravo, Contreras & López 2015).

^[34] Doménech & Gutiérrez 2005, p. 1570; Doménech 2009.

^[35] Flores, Pliego & Carvajal 2013.

^[36] Gozalbes Cravioto 2005.

^[37] Vico, Cores & Cores 2006. Hereafter, *CNV*.

^[38] Vizcaíno 2007, p. 687-714.

^[39] Pliego 2009, p. 188-190.

^[40] Metcalf 1999; Retamero 2005; Huffstot 2006; Martín Viso 2008 and 2015.

^[41] Mateu y Llopis 1958 and 1972.

and the data provided by local researchers and collectors also indicate their rarity. After the publication of Crusafont's work, other sites joined Seville, as we have seen, for example Cartagena, Menorca, Malaga and El Tolmo de Minateda (Hellín, Albacete). The FARMM^[42] has permitted the documentation of an example from Linares (Jaen) – Crusafont included Menjíbar (Jaén) among the uncertain locations – and another one from Posadas (Córdoba).

Apart from these sites and Tolmo de Minateda, most new examples come from the city of Malaga. There are 13 confirmed examples, although according to Mora many coins are still awaiting examination. These examples come from the excavation of Palacio del Obispo-Calle Molina-Calle Larios^[43], Catedral-Calle Cañón-Postigo de los Abades^[44], Museo Picasso, Teatro Romano/Alcazabilla, and Calle Echegaray and Cine Echegaray – near Museo Picasso and Antiguo Colegio de San Agustín, former Facultad de Letras^[45]. There is also some decontextualised material from the metropolitan area, specifically the district of Churriana, which, as aforementioned, has not been included in this work^[46], and neither are the private collections that remain unpublished. According to C. Gozalbes Cravioto^[47], there are other places in the province of Malaga where these coins are found, such as the area around Mount San Antón, Campanillas, in the hills of Ronda and Teba. For our part, through the use of the collection in the FARMM we have confirmed the find of one example in Cañete La Real.

Regarding Cartagena, the two *nummi* that belong to Type 16 – with Cross/Delta – and are mentioned by Crusafont^[48] have now been joined by 20 more^[49], in addition to another example in Muralla de Lorenzo Possi^[50]. Since then, the excavations in the city have yielded numerous more examples, which remain unpublished^[51], although local archaeologists confirm that all of them belong to Type 16^[52]. According to Lechuga^[53], this type had a nominal value of 4 *nummi*, and it has been found in the foundation levels of the Byzantine district built over the theatre, which suggests that these coins started circulating soon after the Byzantine arrival in Cartagena^[54]. In addition to the city of Cartagena, this typology has been recorded in Torre Trencada (Ciutadella, Menorca), Tolmo de Minateda (Albacete) and maybe also the coin (above) from Clermont-Ferrand (France). This series has thus been securely attributed to

^[42] Fondo Arqueológico Ricardo Marsal Monzón (Archaeological Museum of Seville). The collection of the FARMM was compiled in the 1990s and the early 2000s by a private collector, and includes documents, plans and drawings of archaeological sites. Obviously, this documentation must be handled with caution, but it can be used to challenge or support other evidence.

^[43] Marot 2001; Mora 2001a-b.

^[44] Mora & Martínez 2008.

^[45] Mora 2009, p. 248.

^[46] Although I appreciate E. Gozalbes Cravioto's work with this material, and understand that he had little time to carry it out, decontextualised material which does not come from systematic excavations should only be accepted when solid information regarding the material's provenance is forthcoming. Also, in these instances photographs of the coins are essential.

^[47] Gozalbes Cravioto 2005, p. 1191.

^[48] Crusafont 1994, p. 21-22.

^[49] Lechuga & Méndez 1991; Lechuga 2000 and 2005.

^[50] Suárez 2005.

^[51] We want to thank J. Vizcaíno for this information.

^[52] Although Lechuga (2000, p. 348) includes five undetermined examples from the 5th-6th c.

^[53] Lechuga 2005.

^[54] Vizcaíno 2007, p. 709.

the mint of *Carthago Spartaria* during the Byzantine period^[55], a possibility that Crusafont^[56] contemplated, although he never discarded completely a Visigothic filiation and considered that, if Byzantine, the coins were struck on the initiative of the city not the empire.

Despite the importance of these finds, nowhere else has yielded as many Visigothic copper coins as Seville, which is the geographical basis of Crusafont's work. All of his material was decontextualised, but Crusafont underlined several important locations, especially in the historical region of the Aljarafe, the name of which comes from Arabic, meaning a "gently hilled country". Crusafont included coins from Coria del Río – where more examples have been found since then during stratigraphic excavations, as well as at the site of Riopudio^[57] – and San Juan de Aznalfarache and Salteras, where most of Crusafont's examples seem to have come from, probably because his informer was based on the latter town. More recently, a considerable number of examples have been found in other villages in the Aljarafe, such as Palomares del Río, Gelves^[58], Albaida del Aljarafe^[59] and Hacienda Zaudín (Mairena del Aljarafe). Also, Tomares, which is not mentioned by Crusafont, has yielded hundreds of examples, which were found in the plot of land later used for the construction of Aljarafesa^[60]. Many of the examples labelled as coming from 'Seville' were in fact found in these and similar locations.

Near Seville's metropolitan area, Crusafont collected some examples from Montequinto (Dos Hermanas). Crusafont also mentioned the region of Vega del Guadalquivir, specifically the town of Alcalá del Río, to which today we may add the sites of El Cortijo del Coronel (Lora del Río) and Puerto del Barco (Brenes). Regarding the region of Bajo Guadalquivir, Crusafont mentions Utrera; this is also the location of El Palmar de Troya. The FARMM, which was originally located in Herrera, has provided information from the region of Sierra Sur, also in Seville, including Estepa and Osuna, as well as Herrera^[61]. In the Campiña, examples have been found in Montellano. Finally, recent reports indicate the discovery of some examples in Sierra Norte, specifically in the area known as El Cañuelo or La Lapa^[62], between the towns of Guillena and Castilblanco.

Despite this profusion of finds in the province, most contextualised finds have been discovered in the city. Although the importance of finds in stratigraphic excavation can hardly be exaggerated, we must take into consideration that 7th c. ceramic typologies from Seville and other areas in the lower Guadalquivir are still but imperfectly known. Chronologies between the 7th and the 9th c. remain insecure^[63], and the information that examples found in excavation can provide is, therefore, limited. Thus, 7th c. levels are seldom identified, and most sequences stop, at the latest, around the mid-6th c. Examples have been documented

^[55] Lechuga & Méndez 1991.

^[56] Crusafont 1994, p. 22.

^[57] Garrido & Escudero 2013.

^[58] Both in Fernández, Pliego & Carvajal 2013.

^[59] Urbano López (Pers. Comm).

^[60] This includes most of the De la Oliva collection, which is not taken into account in this work.

^[61] Crusafont (1994, p. 22) mentions Osuna but only with regard to a Visigothic ring with an SP monogram which is similar to those found in our Group B.

^[62] In the cadastre, this area is recorded as 'Paraje del Regajo de los Prados'.

^[63] See Domínguez 2006 for the Early Andalusí period (8th-10th c.).

Site/Locality	Province/ Country	Types														Total
		1	2	3-4	5	6-7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	
El Tolmo de Minateda, Hellín	Albacete														1	1
La Punta de L'Arenal, Javea	Alicante			1												1
Posadas	Córdoba			1												1
El Atalayón, Cañete la Real	Málaga					1										14
Catedral. calle Cañón Postigo de los Abades				1		2										
Palacio del Obispo. Calle Molina-Larios						2										
Museo Picasso						2										
Teatro romano/Alcazabilla						5										
Calle y cine Echegaray					1											
Indeterminado	Menorca		2	1	1		2								1	13
Torretrencada, Ciutadella				1											1	
Binigafull, Ciutadella			1													
Son Salomó, Ciutadella			1	1												
Alfurinet, Ciutadella							1									
Teatro romano (Condesa Peralta), Cartagena	Murcia														17	23
Calle Soledad, Cartagena															2	
Pza. Condesa Peralta, Cartagena															2	
Calle Orcel, Cartagena															1	
Muralla de Lorenzo Possi, Cartagena															1	
Cástulo, Linares	Jaén		1													1
Calle San Luis 95	Sevilla			1												296
Calle Sol 115					1											
Calle San Fernando				6												
Pza. de la Encarnación			1		1											
Yacimiento La Reguela, Palomares del Río			32	2	2	1										
Salteras NO			9	3	4	1			1							
San Juan de Aznalfarache			4													
Coria del Río			6													
Rio Pudio, Coria del Río				2												
Salteras			42	8		1										
Alcala del Río			7	4	1	1										
Montequinto, Dos Hermanas			1													
El Palmar de Troya			1													
Albaida																
Cortijo del Coronel, Lora del Río			1													
Cerro de la Higuera, Estepa			1													
Las Cabezuelas, Osuna			1													
Montellano					1											
Castillo de Alhono, Herrera						1										
Indeterminado			2	81	47	6	4		1	1	1	1	1	2	1	
Punta de l'Illa Cullera	Valencia			6	4										10	
Anfiteatro de Arles	Francia				1										1	
Tesoro de Zacha	Grecia				1										1	
Total		2	192	86	22	22	3	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	26	362

Fig. 5 – Recorded finds of Visigothic bronze coins

in Calle San Luis and Calle Sol^[64], Calle San Fernando, Plaza de la Encarnación^[65] and more recently in Plaza de la Pescadería^[66].

As mentioned above, these coins often emerge in association with small-sized Roman coins dating from the 4th c. onwards^[67], as well as with Vandal and Byzantine coins. As we shall see, this is also common in other Mediterranean locations. The following table (fig. 5) summarises the examples known to date – including those in the FARM, which, although they are still unpublished, are documented in the database of the collection. As previously mentioned, on the other hand, the examples from Churriana and those in unpublished – or only partially published – private collections are not included.

A close examination of the find map (fig. 6) confirms that the finds discovered since Crusafont's original publication have done nothing but confirm the geographical trends that he detected. One of T. Marot's^[68] criticisms was that Crusafont underplayed the examples found on the eastern coast and in the territory of the Byzantine province. With the exception

Fig. 6 – Finds map

^[64] Fernández Flores 2003a.

^[65] Fernández Flores, Pliego & Carvajal 2013.

^[66] Pliego & García (forthcoming).

^[67] The circulation of 4th c. coins in the 6th and 7th c. is amply documented in the Mediterranean: Moorhead 2013, p. 605. See Butcher 2002, for Beirut (p. 115), and Reece (2003, p. 219-245) for Carthage.

^[68] Marot 2001, p. 145.

of Cullera – which was not even in the Byzantine territory – the finds in these regions are very scarce, whereas in the south and the region around Seville new examples have continued to emerge. Now, I shall discuss one of the most controversial issues concerning these bronzes.

6. THE CHRONOLOGY

Chronology was one of the key arguments behind T. Marot's rejection of Crusafont's characterisation. This argument was based on the chronology of L'Illa de Cullera. The abandonment or destruction of this settlement is dated to Leovigild's reign (c. 572-586), but these levels yielded six specimens of our Type 3 and four specimens of our Type 4, which Crusafont dated to Wamba's reign (672-680). For Marot, these coins must have been struck before the settlement was abandoned, and must be chronologically close to Justinian I's *nummi*, with which they were found^[69].

This chronological attribution is especially shocking considering that it was Marot herself who revealed that 4th c. imperial coins were still in circulation in the 6th and 7th c., and that early Vandal coins also circulated alongside Justinian's Byzantine *nummi*^[70]. Moreover, the most significant thing about the chronology of L'Illa de Cullera is that it was established on the basis of the coins, specifically Justinian I's, despite the nearby find of 7th c. pottery^[71]. Also, this chronological ascription ignores a coin struck during Wamba's reign, which was found and recorded by Mateu y Llopis^[72], who thereby established that 'the years 672-680 close the numismatic series of L'Illa'^[73]. On top of all of these, the excavators reported that 'the regular presence of late pottery, from between the 5th and the 7th c., in different areas, suggests considerable activity and the presence of an inhabited nucleus throughout Late Antiquity, a nucleus that was open to the Mediterranean and which had the ability to engage in exchange activities'^[74].

For his part, Mora^[75] also dated the bronze coins to the 6th c. on the basis of Justinian I's series and the associated pottery. The archaeologists in charge of the excavation of Plaza del Obispo, in Malaga^[76], believe that this area was transformed into a maritime and commercial area which remained active until the 7th c. The buildings excavated in the area where the coins were found collapsed violently in an event which the excavators associate with the conquest of *Malaca* by Sisebut^[77], in 612-621, probably around 615, that is, in the 7th c. In consequence, we have bronze coins in circulation in Malaga well into the 7th c., which of course means that other similar coins could well be still in circulation elsewhere. The arbitrary dating of

^[69] Marot 2001, p. 145.

^[70] Marot 2001, p. 133-134.

^[71] Roselló & Cotino 2005, p. 140 and 150.

^[72] Mateu y Llopis 1972, p. 252; Barral 1976, p. 189, n° 126.

^[73] Mateu y Llopis 1972, p. 252.

^[74] The pottery assemblage has revealed a wide variety of imported wares, including kitchen wares, tablewares and amphorae. The provenance of these wares is North Africa, Gallia, Italy, Lusitania, Central and Eastern Mediterranean, Ibiza, Catalonia and the SE of the Iberian Peninsula, among others. North Africa, and specifically Tunisia, was the main supply area, including tablewares and bottled products, especially oil and salted fish sauces.

^[75] Mora 2009. Although in 2001a, 450, n° 117 and 2001b, p. 136, he talks about the early 7th c.

^[76] See Navarro *et al.* 2000 with references.

^[77] Navarro, Fernández & Suárez 1997, p. 85 for these authors.

the Malaga bronzes to the 6th c. must, therefore, be based on the conventional chronology of L'Illa de Cullera.

In this regard, authors such as Vizcaíno^[78] have called for caution 'due to the residual nature of many numismatic finds and the subsequent difficulty in defining a solid chronology', an opinion which I endorse^[79]. Following others^[80], B. Mora^[81] detected this phenomenon with regard to Late Imperial bronze coins, for instance in Seville in Calle San Luis and Calle Sol^[82], the Visigothic necropolis in Calle Real, n° 39 (Carmona)^[83], where three 4th c. bronze coins were found^[84], and Riopudio (Coria del Río), where two Visigothic copper coins were found alongside 4th-century Roman pieces.

Despite the fact that the chronological implications of typology have been overlooked, perhaps because of the rigidity of Crusafont's scheme^[85], five conclusions can be extracted:

- Type 2, division: the cross above the steps was introduced during Leovigild's reign, post 578, and was abandoned towards c. 584 and resumed during Recceswinth's reign (c. 653), not to be abandoned again until the last emissions.
- Type 2, multiple: the frontal bust was used on its own from c. 584 to c. 653 and to the end of the Visigothic period in combination with other motifs.
- Types 3-4: This is a bust or head in profile, and there is probably a torso on the reverse, so this type leads to the period just before 584, when it was abandoned until mid 7th c.; but it really doesn't provide a clear chronological information.
- Type 5: Although there exists a rare byzantine *nummus* of Justinian I which observes are similar to this typology^[86] (bust to r. and cross), the bust with cross-shaped sceptre in Visigothic coins appears during Wamba's reign (672-680) and there are no parallels for busts or heads with crosses among the coins struck by Germanic groups. The Merovingian (*MEC* p. 496, n^{os} 551ff.) and Anglo-Saxon (*MEC* p. 516, n^{os} 694ff.) are, also, later than 670^[87].
- There is no additional information for the remaining groups.

The information available, therefore, does not rule out the striking or circulation of these coins throughout the Visigothic period. In fact, despite the baseless dating of the chronology of these bronzes to the 6th c.^[88], which has now been applied to the whole repertoire, the

^[78] Vizcaíno 2007, p. 711.

^[79] Ripollès (2002, p. 195) warned against dating coins 'on the basis of the date of issue, not of loss'.

^[80] Marot 2001, p. 133-134.

^[81] Mora 2003, p. 365-366; 2012, p. 412 and 416.

^[82] Fernández Flores 2003a.

^[83] See Anglada & Conlin 1998, p. 935, 938.

^[84] Although all excavations carried out in Andalusia have to be published in the *Anuario Arqueológico de Andalucía*, until recently coins were not examined in detail and in most cases their discovery is merely mentioned without further details being added.

^[85] Crusafont 1994, p. 32-38.

^[86] Morrisson 1970, p. 106,16-17.

^[87] There are two Merovingian *tremisses* minted in Tolosa which bear the name of the *monetarius Magnus* and which have been dated to before 670 because of being struck in gold (see Lafaurie 1969). However, in my opinion, the very uniqueness of these examples questions such a rigid chronology.

^[88] Mora 2009.

Visigoths were the last Germanic group to issue *nummi*^[89]. If Vandal and Ostrogoth *nummi* still circulated in the Mediterranean in the 6th and even the 7th c., after their kingdoms had disappeared, there is no reason for the Visigoths to still use and, to a lesser extent, issue them until at least the 7th c.

7. THE LOCATION: MINTS?

Earlier, I recalled that one of the key criticisms of Crusafont's work concerned the attribution of different coin types to several cities within the *regnum*^[90]. The lack of agreement on this issue is perfectly justified, with the exception of the groups associated with *Hispalis* (Type 2), but the different authors have, incomprehensively, insisted on adding these attributions to the descriptions, when the name of the groups and types (Groups C, D, E, t. 3-6) would have been enough for the purposes of identification. The lack of evidence is particularly noticeable regarding Group E (Type 6), as Crusafont fails to indicate any epigraphical connection with the toponym *Cordoba*, something that he admitted. In my opinion, in fact, the attribution of other groups to *Emerita* and *Toledo* are equally problematic. At any rate, it is possible to forward some interpretations for Type 6.

As stated earlier, the recent discovery of these numismatic series in Malaga has had a considerable impact on their interpretation. These pieces were found during excavations, and were often found alongside Byzantine coins (Mora 2001a-b). In a more recent publication, Mora has compiled all 'late' coins found in Malaga, including Late Roman, Byzantine and Visigothic. There were a total of 13 Visigothic coins which included one example belonging to Type 3-4 (Crusafont's Group C); the rest were described as belonging to Type 6 (Crusafont's Group E)^[91]. The abundance of the type led B. Mora^[92] to suggest that they may have been struck in Malaga, rather than *Cordoba*, despite the fact that Mora's type is substantially different to Crusafont's 'Cordoban' type. In this regard, the reverse of Crusafont's Group E presents an equilateral cross with forked ends, while the Malaga type presents a cross with bifurcated or trifurcated ends and with globules in quadrants and, maybe, also on the ends of the cross. Also, while the bust on the obverse of Group E (Type 6) is to the left, there is one example in Malaga in which it seems to be to the right.

The identification of Crusafont's and Mora's types seems to originate in a work in which E. Gozalbes Cravioto^[93] published some material from several sites in Churriana (Malaga), which are currently in private collections. This catalogue included 67 coins, which were described according to Crusafont's criteria, but not a single photograph was offered; only the diameter of the coins was given^[94]. Among these, it seems, there were some previously unknown types, the reverses of which were drawn^[95]. These drawings depict the equilateral cross with globules in all quadrants or only in the first, second and third quadrants, according

^[89] Moorhead 2013, p. 603. Although Moorhead followed Mora's chronology which, as we have seen, has no archaeological or numismatic basis.

^[90] Marot & Llorens 1996, p. 161; Marot 2001, p. 146.

^[91] Mora 2009, p. 428.

^[92] Mora 2009, p. 430 and 2012a, p. 127.

^[93] Gozalbes Cravioto 2005.

^[94] See note 46.

^[95] Gozalbes Cravioto 2005, p. 1192.

to Gozalbes Cravioto^[96], who identified this type with Crusafont's Group E (supposedly from *Cordoba*), despite the fact that the reverse of this type presented merely an equilateral cross without globules. Mora followed this identification and suggested a possible origin in Malaga. On the other hand, the examples from Menorca (Moll 2005) also present this kind of reverse.

The main problem with the Malaga pieces is that photographs of only 3 of the 12 examples described as belonging to Group E have been published: two from the excavations in the cathedral^[97] and one from the Roman theatre^[98]. In the former, the iconography on the reverse is hard to decipher, but in the latter the head points clearly to the right, while in Crusafont's examples it points to the left. Mora's^[99] argument to support the identification is that, in contrast to the examples found in Seville^[100], which were 'recovered with no archaeological control at all – as were those recently presented in Menorca – the Malaga examples appear frequently in archaeological contexts'^[101]. As we have seen, however, only 13 examples have been found in Malaga, and the 'frequency' that Mora mentions must, therefore, also include the 67 pieces from Churriana, which were recovered in exactly the same way as Crusafont's 229 examples. On top of this, the Churriana pieces present more than a few problems as far as research is concerned. In addition to all of this, of Cravioto's 67 pieces, only 15 (22.38 %) belong to Group E – which, as has been shown, could very well not correspond with Crusafont's (Type 6) – while 16 (23.88 %) belong to Type 3-4 (Crusafont's Group C) (23.88 %), which, following Crusafont's methodology, would be epigraphically more akin to the name of the city. In my opinion, there is no reason to substitute one unlikely attribution for another which is just as unlikely. Due to the crudity of the pieces, it seems wise to wait for the full publication of all examples – including contextual information and photographs –, which is the only way to ensure that typologies are adequately examined. Also, the possibility that new types will emerge in this way must not be discarded.

It is probable that the problem of attribution is based on a fallacious idea unintentionally introduced by Crusafont, who created the spurious need to link coin issues with an important city. Although the identification of the SP/SPL inscription with *Hispalis* seems to support this idea, this series also demonstrates that those in charge of striking these coins had no problem making a clear reference to the place of emission if they wanted to do so. None of the other typologies seem to allude clearly to a specific city. Therefore, these modest coins could have been struck in any of a large number of cities, towns and even small settlements in the Visigothic kingdom. After all, these coins do not seem to have been conceived to play their role far away from where they were struck; that is, they did not circulate on the provincial – let alone the national – but rather the local level. It is for this reason that the location of the finds is doubly important.

^[96] These features, given the crudity and poor state of preservation of these coins, could well have been caused by poor coining techniques.

^[97] Mora & Martínez 2008, figs. 15 and 17.

^[98] Mora 2005, fig. 23.

^[99] Mora 2012b, p. 418.

^[100] Literally, Mora says 'several points in the Campiña, in Seville', but the fact is that the finds are much more frequent in the Aljarafe, as already pointed out by Crusafont.

^[101] In this quote the author is referring to all groups, not only to Group E.

8. THE ISSUING AUTHORITY

Earlier, we saw that according to Crusafont these emissions could respond to an ‘ecclesiastical initiative tolerated by the crown’^[102] and even a ‘citizen-led emission, done without the involvement of the ruling elite’^[103]. Later authors have added little to this, but rather have followed Marot^[104], who, inspired by Crusafont, thought that these emissions could have been promoted by ‘autonomous governments or ecclesiastical authorities in southern cities’. The only difference between both authors is that, for Crusafont^[105], the emissions would be officially endorsed only *a posteriori*.

All authors are more or less agreed on this, although recently a new possibility has been forwarded. The CNV^[106] has raised the possibility that some authority other than the Visigoths could be behind this emission. This idea has never gone beyond the ‘conference-corridor hypothesis’ level, and has never been published or formally argued. The CNV presents a nonsensical metrological argument, according to which it is impossible for ‘money to have only two denominations and so disparate in value as a *tremissis* and a *nummus*’. Apart from the fact that Crusafont^[107] identified several denominations – *nummus*, 2 1/2 *nummi* and *pentanumion*^[108] – the 5th-century Roman monetary system ‘only consisted of high value gold coins – *solidus*, *semissis*, *tremissis* – and low value base metal *nummi*’^[109]. On the other hand, concerning the issuing authority, the CNV suggests that these series could have been issued by ‘aristocratic oligarchies in the Guadalquivir valley’ – thus echoing Crusafont and Marot – but rather thinks that they were ‘most likely struck in the areas controlled by the Byzantines in *Hispania*’^[110].

Although the latter argument hardly raises a serious issue, because, as we shall see, in *Carthago Spartaria*, and therefore in the Byzantine territory, bronze coins were indeed struck, the CNV sets out an additional argument for the consideration of these series as official Byzantine emissions, which, however subtly, stands in contradiction to the metrological argument. According to this argument, the SP/SPL inscription on Type 2 (Crusafont’s Groups A and B) was not related to the city of *Hispalis* but to *Spania*, the name which the Byzantines used to refer to the Spanish lands under their control. Mora^[111] appears to have given this idea some consideration, although a later work^[112] shows less conviction. In this later work, he says the following about the re-attribution of Crusafont’s ‘Cordoban’ series to Malaga: ‘but it is possible that these bronzes, perhaps inspired by the Byzantine issues of Justinian I and Justin II... may have been issued in Malaga’. We do not know whether, according to Mora, ‘inspired’ is the same as striking the pieces, but if we consider that *Malaca*

[102] Crusafont 1994, p. 64-65.

[103] Crusafont 1994, p. 107.

[104] Marot 2001, p. 145.

[105] Crusafont 1994, p. 64.

[106] CNV, p. 111-116.

[107] Crusafont 1994, p. 45-51.

[108] An idea later endorsed by Mora (2012b,) and Fernández, Pliego & Carvajal (2013), among others.

[109] Moorhead 2013, p. 603.

[110] CNV, p. 115-116. The authors argue: ‘We are not specialists in Byzantine, Vandalic or Late-Roman coins, and so we cannot determine with absolute certainty the identity of these coins but we can say that we personally feel they are not of Visigoth origin’ (CNV, p. 116).

[111] Mora & Martínez 2008, p. 203.

[112] Mora 2009, p. 430, note 34.

was occupied by the Byzantines between c. 555 and c. 615, and if we accept that SP alludes to *Spania*, the issuing authority would have to be the Eastern Roman Empire.

As we shall see later, the circulation of *nummi* seems to have been promoted mostly by the Vandals^[113]; the emission and use of *nummi* is, therefore, a Germanic phenomenon, rather than a Byzantine one. On the other hand, we must keep in mind that although the imperial presence lasted in the Iberian Peninsula for 65 years, all experts agree that effective imperial domination was limited to a narrow coastal strip of land and several strategic strongholds from which to control the Straits. Constant conflict was waged between these cities and the Visigoths and the most important among them were probably Cartagena, *Malaca* and *Asidona*. If, indeed, these are Byzantine emissions, the question immediately arises as to why they are primarily found near Seville, which was never under Byzantine rule^[114]. Also, the type with the letters SP (Type 2) is especially common near Seville. In some cases, as already pointed out by Crusafont^[115], the bottom of the shaft of the letter P was intentionally prolonged to the right in order to represent a nexus LP, which clearly points to *Hispalis*^[116]. Also, we would need to explain why the Byzantines decided to start issuing coinage with the name of a province, something uncommon^[117]. Moreover, if that had been the case, numismatists interested in the Byzantine world would surely have remarked such an interesting oddity^[118].

For his part, Huffstot^[119] followed Crusafont in order to suggest that Leovigild, and maybe Liuva I, authorised certain bishops to strike these bronze coins, which were to be circulated within their own dioceses. In 2007, Doménech^[120] revisited this issue in a paper on medieval coins recovered in excavation, which was presented during the 13th national numismatic conference. Doménech's paper included the most recent finds in relation to the series presented by Crusafont in 1994, including a specimen from El Tolmo de Minateda (Albacete), belonging to Type 16 – 'Cross/Delta' – and attributed to Cartagena, which had been published previously^[121]. In Doménech's opinion, the evidence for the *Hispalis* mint is strong, but 'the attribution of these coppers remains open, and only future, secure finds will provide the solution'^[122]. In my opinion, what remains open is the attribution of the known series, apart from those which are related to Seville, to a city. As Doménech^[123] points out,

^[113] For this issue, see Morrison 2003 and 2012.

^[114] For the geographical dimensions of the Byzantine province of *Spania*, see Vizcaino 2007, p. 125-277.

^[115] Crusafont 1994, p. 32.

^[116] Although the most common form in Visigothic coins is *Hispalis*, in Leovigild's earlier series it is *Spali* (Pliego 2009, t. I, p. 118-119).

^[117] According to Grierson (1982, p. 20) "Byzantine mint authorities made only occasional efforts to indicate where and when coins were struck" and the allusions to the name of cities are limited to 'special regions' as Cyprus (*MIB* III, p. 198) – *folles* during Heraclius' reign – and Sicily (Laiou & Morrisson 2007, p. 86) – counting with an emission of *decanummi* by Mauritius Tiberius (582-602), which refers to Sicilia (*MIB* I, 136-137), and the peculiar *folles* from the reign of Heraclius (610-641), contermarked with the mark of *Sicilia* (SCLS) (*MIB* III, p. 104) – as well as the S which refers to Sardinia – from c. 690 to c. 720. For the contermarked *folles* with SCL see Prigent 2006.

^[118] Authors as Morrisson 1996, p. 188; Arslan 2007, p. 25 and 2010, p. 24; Moorhead 2013, among others, have not questioned the Visigothic filiation of these coins.

^[119] Huffstot 2006, p. 15.

^[120] Doménech 2009, p. 736.

^[121] Doménech & Gutiérrez 2005.

^[122] Doménech 2009, p. 739.

^[123] Doménech 2009, p. 738.

the archaeological context within which these coins are found permits their chronological and geographical characterisation^[124], for example with the *Hispalis* series already identified by Crusafont. In my opinion, however, the new information so gathered can hardly be used to challenge the series' cultural ascription, as hinted at by Doménech. Thus far, in fact, the evidence seems to confirm their Visigothic filiation, at least with regard to the only case that has been proven to date, that of *Hispalis*, quite regardless of who ordered the striking of the coins, which would, in any case, be part of the administrative structure of the Visigothic *regnum*.

Apart from the works cited thus far, other authors have analysed the issue of the Visigothic coppers outside the field of numismatics. F. Retamero^[125], for example, focused on the question of the issuing authority and reached the conclusion that 'the examples found in Menorca ... reject for once and for all' their Visigothic filiation, 'unless connections between Menorca and the Visigothic state which could sustain the circulation of money are adequately proven'. On the other hand, I. Martín Viso, among others, has simply dismissed the existence of these series and claimed that 'although the possibility of Visigothic series of coppers has been put forth, the reality is that Late Roman coppers and bronzes remained in circulation for a long time'^[126]. This, being true, does not explain the nature of the series now under consideration. Martín Viso's perspective, which claims the support of scientific consensus against Crusafont's thesis^[127], maybe responds to the difficulty of fitting the Visigothic coppers into his interpretation of the fiscal role of Visigothic coins, which in my opinion is entirely unnecessary^[128]. Once more, the main problem seems to rest with the issuing authority: although Martín Viso flatly states that 'the Visigothic kings only coined gold', he admits that 'at a push, we could accept the issuing of coins by urban authorities, maybe acting autonomously and with the purpose of promoting commercial exchange'. That is, we are back to Crusafont's ideas.

9. THE CIRCULATION OF BRONZES IN THE 6TH AND 7TH C.

Nearly 30 years ago, Grierson and Blackburn^[129] claimed that: 'There are many features of early medieval coinage that seem strange to the historian, and sometimes anomalous even to the numismatist [...] Clearly no simple answer can be given to the question of how the *ius monetae*^[130] fared in Germanic successor states. In none of them was it preserved in a simple and undivided form.' This quote adequately explains the controversy around our series. The application of schemes borrowed from other periods, as well as the consideration of the Iberian Peninsula as a geographical undivisible unit, during a period as unstable as Late Antiquity, seems to have reached 'the numismatist', as predicted by Grierson and Blackburn. Moreover, the stubborn adherence to the view that the Visigoths could have coined anything other than gold coins overlooks the variety of the coins struck by similar cultural groups. A quick glance at the table below (fig. 7) will suffice to show that homogeneity was absent even within a single group. Most of them evolved over time and introduced new metals and

[124] Doménech 2009, p. 738.

[125] Retamero 2005, p. 4.

[126] Cit. Crusafont 1994.

[127] Martín Viso 2008, note 5 and 2015.

[128] Pliego 2009, t. I, p. 230.

[129] *MEC*, p. 4-5.

[130] The right to issue coins.

People	Dates	Metals-Alloy/ Name(s) in Legends												Character		
		Au					Ag					Ae				
		NEmp	King	E&K	Other	Mint	NEmp	King	E&K	Other	Mint	NEmp	King		Other	Mint
Visigoths	c.417-c. 568														?	Ps-Imperial
	?-568															Ps-Imperial/ Municipal/ Local
	c. 569-578															Ps-Imperial/ Regal/ Municipal (Hispalis)/ Local?
	c. 579-601															Regal (Ermenegild, Recared?)/ Municipal (Hispalis)/ Local?
	c. 601-7 th c.?															Regal/Municipal/ Local?
Suevi	c.435-585															Regal
Vandals	440-c.490															Ps-Imperial
	490-533															Regal
	480-533															Municipal (Carthage)
Burgundian	473-532															Regal
Ostrogoths	474-491															Municipal (Rome)
	493-526															Ps-Imperial/Regal Municipal (Ravenna)
	536-554															Regal
	536-554															Ps-Imperial/Non regal
Francs/ Merovingian	500-?587															Non regal
	587?-c.670															
	c. 670 onw.															
Lombards	568-690															Ps-Imperial/Local
Anglo-Sax.	590-675															Regal

Fig. 7 – Germanic monetary systems according to metal used and nature of series. Abbreviations: Au: Gold; Ag: Silver; Æ: Bronze; Emp: Emperor; E&K: Emperor & King; Municip.: Municipal; Ps-Imperial: Pseudo-Imperial

denominations. On the other hand, although some common features exist, uniformity cannot be found concerning the issuing authority.

The table reveals that no Vandal gold coins were struck^[131] and that, despite being issued for only a short time, up to four varieties of silver and copper coins existed: the ‘pseudo-imperial siliquae’, the ‘quasi-imperial siliquae’, the ‘royal issues’ and ‘the municipal copper coinage’^[132]. On the other hand, although the early emissions bore the name of the emperor

^[131] According to Morrisson (2012, p. 149), ‘in ossequio al privilegio imperiale del controllo sul metallo prezioso e a un’ autorità ecumenica che essi speravano – o almeno Genserico sperava – di rivestire’.

^[132] MEC, p. 20ff. For Vandal coins, see Morrisson 1987 and 2003. For the coin-based evidence of the integration of Vandal and Byzantine Africa into Mediterranean commerce, see Morrisson 2012.

(c. 440-c. 490), it was soon replaced by that of the Vandal king. Grierson & Blackburn^[133] have pointed out that Carthage's municipal emissions probably coexisted with a mixture of 'unofficially minted copper *nummi*'^[134]. The Ostrogoths, for their part, coined in all three metals^[135], including municipal series in Rome and Ravenna^[136]. Although the Ostrogoths included the king's name, this also appeared alongside the emperor's, except for bronze coins, on which the king's name appeared on its own. The Burgundians included the emperor's name on their gold coins and the king's on their silver and bronze pieces^[137]. Concerning the Franks, the situation is more complex under the Merovingian dynasty, a 'pseudo-imperial' and 'national' period that lasted until c. 670 and during which they issued *solidi* and *tremisses*, along with the so-called *early minuti argentei* and the silver and bronze coins of Provence and Burgundy^[138]. Afterwards, they struck only silver – *denarii* and obols. It is interesting to note that these coins have been considered 'essentially non-royal in character' because the emissions were barely controlled. In fact, only a small fraction of all the coins struck bear the name of the monarch^[139] – Merovingian coins can reflect the name of minters, ecclesiastical authorities, civil officials, private persons, etc. – despite the fact that they were among the first people to substitute the name of the king for the emperor's on gold coins^[140]. Concerning the Suevi and the Lombards, gold and silver coins are known, and non-official bronze series have been proposed for them^[141]. Regarding the Lombardic Italy's *nummi* latter, Arslan^[142] considers that these emissions were an unofficial (illegal or tolerated) series, produced in response to monetary needs that could not, or would not, be met by official coins.

When analysing this varied numismatic panorama and the numerous emissions of bronze coins, we must never lose sight of the fact that the Roman-Byzantine system did not strike *nummi* in significant numbers until after the conquests of Belisarius in 533, with the beginning of a series, which was to last until Maurice's reign (582-602), in Carthage^[143]. Generally, these coins have been interpreted as a response to local demand during the Vandal domination of North Africa^[144]. In this regard, although Anastasius' reforms attempted to displace the *nummus*, this target was never achieved, and it has been claimed that 'a separate *nummus* economy operating from that of large denominations [may have existed] in the sixth century'^[145]. According to Moorhead, this could reflect the refusal of Mediterranean merchant communities to give up the denomination^[146]. On the other hand, based on the analysis of

^[133] MEC, p. 420, nos 34-42.

^[134] MEC, p. 19.

^[135] For Ostrogothic coins, see Arslan 1978.

^[136] MEC, p. 428, 92ff. and 145ff.

^[137] MEC, p. 75.

^[138] MEC, p. 102.

^[139] MEC, p. 90.

^[140] There are doubts regarding a *tremissis* with the name of Thierry I (511-534) (MEC, p. 187, 471), although a *solidus*? bearing Theodebert I's (534-548) name is beyond question.

^[141] Arslan (2002), against Asolati (2006 and 2008). See also Arslan 2007.

^[142] Arslan 2007, p. 11.

^[143] Moorhead 2013, p. 602, 609.

^[144] Reece 2003, p. 237; Morrison 2012, p. 150.

^[145] Moorhead 2014, p. 20. Following Callu 1979, p. 12-14; Adelson and Kustas 1964, p. 170-171; Butcher 2001-2002, p. 102. See also Moorhead 2007, p. 298.

^[146] Moorhead 2013, p. 609-610 and 2014, p. 20.

material from the ancient city of *Buthrotum* (current Butrint, Albania), Moorhead presents an interesting panorama on the use of the *nummus* in the Mediterranean and concludes that this denomination is essential for the understanding of the Mediterranean economy in Late Antiquity. Until the 6th c., *nummi* from diverse origins – Roman, Byzantine, Vandal and Ostrogoth, as well as irregular *nummi* – circulated inside bags^[147], the value of which was calculated by weight, and which were opened only for small transactions. It is peculiar that, because of their low denomination, they could be adapted to every system^[148], which explains their wide dissemination throughout the Mediterranean. Moreover, Moorhead^[149] has pointed out that the economy of the *nummus* seems to be a coastal Mediterranean phenomenon. Significant collections of *nummi* in the Central and the Eastern Mediterranean have been found in Fontana Liri in Frosinone^[150], Dalmatia^[151] and Butrint^[152] in the Balkans, Zacha in the Peloponnese^[153], Sardis in Asia Minor^[154], Beirut^[155] and Gush Halav^[156] in the Near East, Qau el-Kebir in Egypt^[157] and Sidi Aïch and Aïn Kelba^[158] in North Africa, among many others^[159]. In the Western Mediterranean, we may mention L’Illa de Cullera^[160], which must have been open to Mediterranean commerce^[161] and Seville^[162].

10. THE VISIGOTHIC MONETARY SYSTEM: GOLD, SILVER AND BRONZE

Only the Visigoths and the Merovingian Theudebert I (534-548) included the king’s name on gold coins. Around 578-580, Leovigild’s name was on the reverse of *tremisses*, the obverse of which bore the name of Justin II, which disappeared soon after. Thereafter, and in contrast to the Merovingian series, gold Visigothic coins were eminently regal, bearing only the name of the king up to the last days of the *regnum*^[163]. The Visigoths also issued silver coins, but this was abandoned around the reign of Leovigild^[164].

^[147] This is suggested by the written record – in which these bags are referred to as *follis* – and mosaic depictions (Moorhead 2013, p. 605).

^[148] Moorhead 2013, p. 609.

^[149] Moorhead 2014, p. 21.

^[150] Arslan 1986.

^[151] *RIC X*, p. cxxxvii.

^[152] Moorhead 2007 and 2014.

^[153] Adelson & Kustas 1964.

^[154] Buttrey *et al.* 1981, p. 123-124; Burrell 2007.

^[155] *RIC X*, p. cxxxi.

^[156] Bijovsky 1998.

^[157] Milne 1926.

^[158] Lafaurie 1959 and Morrisson 1980, respectively.

^[159] For an analysis of *nummus* hoarding, see Asolati (2012). On the other hand, the circulation of 4th c. Roman coins throughout the 5th and 6th c. has been demonstrated by recent excavations in Gortyna (Garraffo 1996, p. 182-183), Beirut (Butcher 2001-2002), Carthage (Reece 2003, p. 219-245), Zilil (Depeyrot 1999, p. 58) and Butrint (Moorhead 2007, p. 294-295; Moorhead 2014, p. 21).

^[160] Mateu y Llopis 1958 and 1972.

^[161] Roselló & Cotino 2005, p. 150.

^[162] Seville, although not mentioned in the text, is included on Moorhead’s map ‘Mints producing *nummi* in the late Roman and early periods, c. AD 300-700’ (See Moorhead 2013, p. 604).

^[163] See Pliego 2009, t. II.

^[164] Recently Crusafont *et al.* 2015.

Regarding bronze, and according to the available evidence, I think that several series may be attributed to the Visigoths. In my opinion, the series with the inscription *ERM*^[165] (Type 1) can be interpreted as an official issue during Hermenegild's reign (579-584). Other monarchs are known to have been named on *nummi*, for example Odoacer (476-493)^[166], the Ostrogoth Totila (541-552)^[167], the Vandal Gelimer (530-534)^[168], the Burgundian Gundobald (473-516)^[169] and of course the Merovingians Thierry I (511-534)^[170], Theudebert I (534-548)^[171] and Childebert I (511-558)^[172]. It is, therefore, not unlikely that Hermenegild, who had been made heir to his father's throne in 579 and who ruled the Baetica from *Hispalis*, promoted, or simply tolerated, the issuing of bronze coins with his name. Their use in the city and province, at any rate, seems to be proven by the evidence. We must also keep in mind that, after revolting against his father, Hermenegild dared to issue two series of *tremisses* bearing his name. The fact that all of these types are so scarce must be connected with this monarch's tragic end^[173].

On the other hand, the series with the inscription SP, of which two denominations exist (Type 2), is, in my opinion, an official municipal series from *Hispalis*. Although other official series must not be disregarded, this is the only one known to date in which the name of the city is expressed clearly, and is in this regard similar to the series issued in Rome and Ravenna by the Ostrogoths, among others. The cross above steps on the reverse of the low-denomination type and the frontal bust of the high-denomination type are reminiscent of types that post-date 578 and c. 584, respectively, and in consequence were issued during Leovigild's reign. It is, therefore, likely that Hermenegild's emission set the precedent for other official emissions from *Hispalis*, which was the royal court of kings Theudis and Athanagild^[174] and the epicentre of Hermenegild's rebellion. The political centrality of Seville is explained by the strength of its nobility, including such outstanding figures as S^t Leander and S^t Isidore^[175]. In this regard, during Late Antiquity the oligarchy of the city underwent a considerable process of growth which was closely connected with the power of the Church. This oligarchy was, to a large extent, responsible for the maintenance of commercial links with the Mediterranean, as documented by the ceramic wares present in the archaeological record^[176].

In addition to this well-known series, a few years ago I published an example which presented a monogram on both the reverse and the obverse (Type 15)^[177]. One of the monograms is a clear allusion to *Hispalis* (S, P, Λ, L). On the other, the letters "R, C, D" can be clearly distinguished, while a fourth letter is not quite so clear, although it could well be another "R". At the time, I suggested a connection with the city of Córdoba, but now I believe that the reference may

^[165] Crusafont 1994, Addenda, p. 108.

^[166] MEC, p. 422, n° 64.

^[167] MEC, p. 434, n° 157 and ff.

^[168] MEC, p. 420, n° 28 and ff.

^[169] MEC, p. 460, n° 339.

^[170] MEC, p. 471, n° 388.

^[171] See the Fitzwilliam Museum website (CM.PG.16118-2006).

^[172] MEC, p. 471, n° 391.

^[173] Pliego 2009, t. II, n°s 61-62.

^[174] Ripoll 2000, p. 374.

^[175] See the entry for 'Sevilla' in García Moreno 1974.

^[176] García Vargas & Vázquez 2006.

^[177] Pliego 2009, t. I, p. 189, fig. 108.

be to another king, one who was, moreover, chronologically close to Hermenegild: Reccared. If this is correct, this piece probably represents an official series issued in Seville – since that monogram presents no difficulties of interpretation – in Reccared’s name.

There is little doubt that Seville was one of the most important cities during the Visigothic period, but its location on a navigable river that reached the centre of the city until at least the 9th c.^[178] also turned it into the most suitable harbour for commercial contacts with the Mediterranean. The presence of ceramic imports from the Eastern Mediterranean, Italy and North Africa, found along with other foreign materials – such as Greek marbles – suggests the continuation of commercial ties and the need to maintain harbour facilities, even if on a smaller scale than in previous periods^[179]. The trading activity also left traces in the written record, with records concerning the collection of customs duties – *vectigalia* – and the existence of commercial courts – *telonea* – where commercial suits were solved by specialised officials – *telonarii*^[180]. In addition, it is known that an important Eastern community settled in the city in the 3rd c., and that its commercial importance did not wither away with the invasions, as had happened in coastal cities^[181], as demonstrated by the arrival of Eastern commercial vessels in 456^[182]. The importance of Seville’s harbour is also described by Procopius^[183], who gives an account of the arrival of Carthaginian merchants also in the 6th c.^[184]. In this regard, the coastal nature of the circulation of *nummi* that Moorhead^[185] suggests would situate Seville within an essentially coastal framework which included the coast of the southern Iberian Peninsula and the Byzantine-controlled areas^[186].

It is worth mentioning briefly that E. García Vargas^[187] recently pointed out the possibility of the SP series being related to the activity of the harbour or to commercial transactions carried out within the city-controlled markets^[188]. On the other hand, the concentration of finds in Seville and its hinterland seems to confirm beyond doubt the association between the series and the city (see fig. 8) and to render unnecessary, therefore, any further arguments against the filiation of these coins and the Byzantine province of *Spania*.

The remaining typologies can also either be municipal emissions, whereby the monograms and letters point to other cities or towns – interpretation is far from complete – or local, non-official emissions, which are associated with local political or religious authorities – maybe bishops who preferred for some reason not to mention their see –, as originally suggested by

^[178] See Cabrera 2015, p. 234.

^[179] García Vargas & Vázquez 2006.

^[180] García Moreno 1991, p. 387.

^[181] See Vizcaíno 2007, p. 311-312 with references.

^[182] Hydatius, *Chron.* 177.

^[183] *Bell. Vand.* I, 24, 7 and ff.

^[184] See García Moreno (1972, p. 137). See also García Vargas 2015.

^[185] Moorhead 2014, p. 21.

^[186] *Gades*, which had traditionally been the main harbour in the area of the Straits, went into sharp decline from the 3rd c. onwards (Bernal 2010). The role which the city had played was thereafter assumed by other locations in the Bay of Gibraltar. Similarly, Cartagena and *Malaca* recovered somewhat during the Byzantine period, but they never reached their previous levels of activity (Vizcaíno 2007, p. 294). In fact, some authors question the role played by the Byzantines in the commercial revival of the Spanish coasts, and claim that it promoted the arrival of Mediterranean products only to a ‘very modest’ extent (see Ripoll 1998, p. 234. cit. in Vizcaíno 2007, p. 294).

^[187] García Vargas 2015, p. 195.

^[188] For a vision of Seville during Late Antiquity, see García Vargas 2015.

Fig. 8 – Number of specimens according to typology and location of find, with logarithmic scale

Crusafont. Following what I explained earlier about the importance of Seville's harbour and the likely existence of markets elsewhere in the province, more attention should be paid to the region of the Aljarafe. This sector has operated throughout history as the natural zone of expansion for the city, and as a resource catchment area^[189]. As we have seen, it is also the area where most of our bronzes are to be found. The most recent archaeological information suggests that the region remained active during Late Antiquity, when occupation tended to concentrate near the river, especially in the Aljarafe^[190]. Some authors have pointed out that the decreasing navigability of the Guadalquivir River worked in favour of the Aljarafe^[191]. Be that as it may, the fact is that archaeology presents a picture of commercial vitality, not only with the import of North African and Eastern Mediterranean products 'but also the likely commercialisation of products from the Aljarafe to other areas in the Western Baetica and even other, more distant, areas of the Empire'^[192]. It is worth mentioning that in the Aljarafe there are more Christian inscriptions dated to between the 5th and the 7th c. than there are pagan ones, which leads Beltrán & Escacena^[193] to stress the presence in the area of an active and wealthy agricultural population during that period. The excavation of Riopudio, in Coria del Río^[194], points in the same direction: the archaeologists have suggested that, based on the site's growth during the Late Roman period, Riopudio should be identified with a *mansio* or even a prosperous market^[195]. Finally, we must not forget the importance of *Osset* – modern San Juan de Aznalfarache – one of the most important locations in the Aljarafe and an important landmark in the civil war between Leovigild and Hermenegild.

Therefore, it seems clear that the production of our series was restricted to the south, and was especially common in Seville: as shown in fig. 9, the Type 2 from *Hispalis* is the most common. Also, it is the location where the largest number of the different groups has been found, including the only two known pieces with Hermenegild's name, and the Groups 3-4 and 5 – the latter was also found in Zacha's hoard and the amphitheatre of Arles^[196] (fig. 10). Although I have previously said that Hermenegild's (Type 1) series may have encouraged those from *Hispalis* (Types 2 and 15), it is also possible that the emission of these small bronzes is an earlier phenomenon, before the Visigothic monarchy was stable and had to struggle with other civil and religious powers for authority in the former Roman cities^[197]. Finally, fig. 10 illustrates that the majority of the finds (81.77 %) are concentrated in the city and province of Seville, with the exceptions of Types 7, 8 – only found in Menorca^[198] – and 16, which have been attributed to Cartagena, as we shall see shortly.

Concerning Cartagena, bronzes with the typology 'Cross /Delta' (Type 16) have been attributed to the city on the basis of the location of the finds. This typology alone is deserving of a study. According to archaeological evidence, they should be dated to the mid-6th c. (c. 555), that is, during the Byzantine occupation. The production of the type therefore started

[189] Beltrán & Escacena 2003, p. 400.

[190] Beltrán & Escacena 2003, p. 400.

[191] Ruiz *et al.* 2014, p. 99-100.

[192] Ruiz *et al.* 2014, p. 99-100; quot. Remesal 1991.

[193] Beltrán & Escacena 2003, p. 397-398.

[194] Garrido & Escudero 2013.

[195] Garrido & Escudero 2013, p. 47.

[196] Depeyrot 1983, n° 31 ; Marot 2001, p. 145.

[197] I want to thank E. García Vargas for this suggestion.

[198] Although the 'frontal bust' described by Moll (2005) is not particularly conspicuous.

Fig. 9 – Total number of coins found according to typology

Fig. 10 – Percentage of finds according to location

before those of *Ermenegildo* (Type 1) and *Hispalis* (Type 2), which must have begun around 580. Despite this chronology, the numismatist who has studied this type most intensively is not convinced by the idea of an official Byzantine issue, due to ‘the total absence of any reference to the authority or ruler behind these emissions’^[199]. Thus, he suggests an emission promoted by the influential mercantile class of the city, maybe with some support from the Church^[200]. Along the lines of my own argument, these coins would then be a local issue conceived to address local needs. This explains that, although isolated examples have been

^[199] Lechuga 2000, p. 339.

^[200] Lechuga 2000, p. 342.

found elsewhere – two examples in Menorca and one in Tolmo de Minateda – the circulation of the series is almost exclusively local^[201]. In conclusion, although their emergence may be related to the city's revival after the Byzantine conquest, if these coins were official, their typology would reflect that nature more explicitly.

A similar argument may be applied to Malaga, even if the number of pieces is smaller and, of the 13 examples found during excavations, we have only three photographs, which makes it hard to decide. On the other hand, it is necessary to determine the exact nature of the recurrent type, which seems not to be the same as in Seville – head to left and no globules – or Menorca (frontal bust; Type 8). Once all examples, including those from Churriana, are adequately published, it will be possible to paint a more precise picture, and there is nothing to rule out a municipal emission in Malaga.

On the other hand, we know that the Balearic Islands played a key role in the operation of Mediterranean commercial networks, at least between the 4th and the 6th c. The ceramic finds from L'Illa de Cullera have been related to these commercial links with the islands^[202], and the numismatic evidence could point in the same direction. Menorca, therefore, could be a crucial link for the Mediterranean exchange network, as seemingly suggested by the Byzantine, Vandal and Visigothic *nummi* found on the island.

Taking into account all of this evidence, and in order to address one of the most controversial issues, I believe that there is nothing to stop us calling these series Visigothic. Foreign specialists, perhaps more accustomed to the study of early medieval coins, have had no qualms in referring to them as such^[203], in the same way that Ostrogoth and Vandal emissions are labelled 'Ostrogoth' and 'Vandal' regardless of which is the actual authority behind the emission – urban, local or religious. It is only in more specific studies that further detail is rendered necessary: for instance, with Vandal coins the authors refer to 'semi-autonomous

Fig. 11 – Percentage of finds according to historical regions. Variables with a value of 0 % have been excluded from the graphic

^[201] Lechuga 2000, p. 339.

^[202] Vizcaíno 2007, p. 295.

^[203] See note 117.

copper coinage of Carthage', and with Ostrogoth *folles* and *semi-folles* to 'Municipal bronze coinage of Rome' or 'Municipal bronze coinage of Ravenna'. It seems, therefore, that the phenomenon is typically found among Germanic peoples, as also demonstrated by the concentration of finds in the Visigothic areas (fig. 11).

There are many aspects and questions that still need to be addressed – typological and comparative analysis, economic function, etc. – but this is not the place for such an in-depth analysis. My intention has been merely to revisit the material, review the controversy and, first and foremost, the 'numismatic situation' following the Germanic invasions. A comprehensive corpus that includes all known examples, some of which remain unpublished, is in the process of being compiled, and all these questions will have to be more fully addressed there. I hope, at least, to have presented the basic elements with which to identify the series which cannot be attributed to a specific city with the evidence currently available. In addition, and aware that this is perhaps a tall order, I hope that enough arguments have been provided to end once and for all the stubborn reluctance of many to consider these emissions as part of the Visigothic corpus.

11. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, I have endeavoured to present some numismatic series which, when they were first published nearly 30 years ago, were indifferently received by Spanish specialists. The comparison between these and similar emissions in other Germanic kingdoms disqualifies the arguments based on the implausibility of a monetary system that includes anything other than gold *tremisses*. The use of *nummi* throughout the Mediterranean until at least the 6th c. is related to the commercial network created after the foundation of the Vandal kingdom in North Africa. In line with typical practices in Late Antique Europe, these Visigothic series were backed by a variety of issuing authorities. This is not the case with the bronzes that carry the inscription ERM, which could be an official series issued on Hermenegild's orders in *Hispalis* around 579. Seville was Hermenegild's political seat and the centre of his coup against his father, King Leovigild. It is likely that this series encouraged the emission of a municipal series, which was probably also official, with the name of the city being alluded to by the inscriptions SP and SPL – one in each of the two denominations. The typology seems to point to Leovigild's reign, after 584. *Hispalis* was not only one of the most important cities in the Visigothic *regnum* but its fluvial harbour also enjoyed ideal conditions for the Mediterranean trade. In addition to the official series, the region of Seville witnessed the emergence of a number of unofficial emissions, which were probably promoted by local or religious authorities and tolerated by the Crown. It seems likely that the lively commercial activity of the city and the circulation of *nummi* spilled into the surrounding areas, especially the Aljarafe, where most of the finds are concentrated. However, it is also possible that the emission and use of *nummi* is an earlier phenomenon fostered by religious authorities, hence the lack of any explicit reference to location, and that the practice was adopted by the city of Seville only after Hermenegild's arrival.

In this sense, although the series from *Carthago Spartaria*, must have been struck during the Byzantine period, that is, earlier than the official series from the Baetica, they could be coeval with other emissions which, as aforementioned, were struck before the reign of Hermenegild. In any case, this series from Cartagena also seems to be municipal in character, tolerated but not ordered by the ruler, as suggested by the absence of any explicit references to it. Circulation seems to be local, since no specimens have been found far away, although new finds could change this perspective. The case of *Malaca* is more doubtful, because the evidence is rather muddled. At any rate, the possibility of a municipal emission similar to Cartagena's cannot be disregarded.

In any case, it seems clear that these emissions, at least the majority of them, were not directly dependent on the imperial authorities in the Iberian Peninsula, but rather on the commercial involvement of individual cities. It seems obvious that the production, use and circulation of these coins in the Visigothic regions occurred in response to a demand for small denominations, as also seen in other Mediterranean regions, and that this demand did not cease after the expulsion of the Byzantines during Suintila's reign. This continuity is hardly surprising, for Visigothic coin issues were among the most consolidated, regular and durable of those produced in the Germanic kingdoms.

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